

THE MAGIC OF THE BRUSH

Jo'rayev Muhammadqodir Qahramon o'g'li

In the name of Kamoliddin Behzod
National Institute of Art and Design 2nd stage student.

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Abstract. *In this article, the author talks about the great work of small creators, the beautiful and unique nature of our country, animal world, ancient monuments, structures built in the years of independence, national values and traditions. The relevance of the topic of the article is expressed in the insufficient study of the scientific approach in visual arts, which is closer to scientific knowledge than other types of artistic perception of the world, and inconsistency of research evaluation.*

Key words: *Brush, Painting, watercolor, gouache, tempera, watercolor, colored glass, colored stone, decoration, monumental art, monumental painting, easel art, animalistics, historical genre, domestic genre, batal genre, specially treated fabric, wood, paper, cardboard, glass, metal.*

ВОЛШЕБСТВО КИСТИ

Аннотация. *В данной статье автор рассказывает о великом труде маленьких творцов, красивой и уникальной природе нашей страны, животном мире, древних памятниках, сооружениях, построенных в годы независимости, национальных ценностях и традициях. Актуальность темы статьи выражается в недостаточной изученности научного подхода в изобразительном искусстве, который ближе к научному знанию, чем другие виды художественного восприятия мира, и противоречивости исследовательской оценки.*

Ключевые слова: *Кисть, Живопись, акварель, гуашь, темпера, акварель, цветное стекло, цветной камень, декор, монументальное искусство, монументальная живопись, станковое искусство, анималистика, исторический жанр, бытовой жанр, батальный жанр, специально обработанная ткань, дерево, бумага, картон, стекло, металл.*

Fine art is my hobby, I don't choose a subject. I enjoy creating by the water. "Sunset on the Beach" is my first painting depicting the sunset by the lake I still remember. Natural landscapes, wonders of the animal world are a source of inspiration for me. Being a skilled artist, I want to show the beauty of my country to the whole world through fine arts.

I am currently studying easel painting at the institute. Let me tell you about the painting. A painting is a work of art created on a solid surface using colored materials, such as paints. Artistic representation and interpretation of painted reality; an important means of influencing the thoughts and feelings of the audience; has important social content and diverse ideological functions. The artistic content of a painting is embodied in its theme and plot, the plot is realized by the artist through means of expression of the painting (composition, composition, color, rhythm, etc.).

Paintings are made of a base (specially treated fabric, wood, paper, cardboard, glass, metal, etc.), a layer of color (watercolor, gouache, tempera, watercolor, colored glass, colored stone, etc.), some In some cases, it consists of a thin layer of varnish on top of it to preserve it. Color (color) is an important visual and impact tool of painting. Through color, the artist depicts the existence or

imaginary world in visible forms, can show the infinity of space, the variety of colors, materiality, volume and texture of things in it, can reflect movement, changes in the human psyche, complex emotional experiences, and thoughts. The means of pictorial expression and working method of the color image depend on the color used, the characteristics of the tools, color solvents, and the base (for example, depending on whether the surface is smooth or rough, the appearance of the work can have different effects). The work is created in the form of a draft of an idea that first appeared in the imagination and mind of the creator, in pencil or charcoal, on a surface (often paper and cardboard). Then a suitable base is selected and treated according to the nature of the work to be done.

After that, the picture is processed by specifying the position of the image. When coloring, it is possible to start with a gradually diluted color and make it multi-layer or one-layer when applying the desired color. The processing of painting works can be conventionally divided into two - flat and volumetric - spatial styles: in the first style, the image is processed in solid flat forms without light, and in the volume-spatial method, the image is depicted in a manner related to the environment with the help of a volumetric light.

of the world scientific and artistic the development of science and of art some common laws own into in receiving manifestation will be Only that's it because of science and of art a person of activity opposite two to the field division relative character occupation is enough As the French writer and artist Jean Cocteau said: "Art is the exact science"[1]. As an example of this, the ancient Greek culture, the history of European thought has been going on for a long time Ptolemy Pythagoras, Pascal, Leibniz, Locke, Voltaire, Montesque such as of representatives in person scientific-aesthetic, research and to the truth artistic approaches in the middle sure difference from absence proof will give. Science and of art two different independent in actions formed the time guess to do possible it's not. Humanity of activity all fields of science and art sure separation in the 20th century, this division wide public attention drew and scientific research to the subject has become from the time started " The artist historian, poet, philosopher or observer to be can And this truth: all great artists together knowledgeable people was,"he said Russian writer AA Bestuzhev Marlinsky.

Such works are rich in color, in which it is possible to feel all shades of colors, to see the reflected color of the incident light, and the reflection of the reflected rays and enrichment with other colors (reflex). There is no strict boundary between these two styles in paintings, one complements the other. Painting works are monumental (monumental art, monumental painting), decorative (decorative art, decorative art), machine art, decoration, depending on the location, content, function, style and appearance of the painting. (theatrical and cinema decoration), miniature and others. The image is divided into a number of genres depending on the subject and direction of the content: animalistics, historical genre, domestic genre, field genre, portrait, landscape, still life and others can be taken as an example.

Conclusion. Modern art seeks new ways of development, strives to establish stable life values. Art is only valuable if it is an expression of morality. This connection remains significant today. Art develops not under the influence of one or another leading ideas, trends, abstract worldview, but under the influence of the culture of its time. In general, when creating beauty with colors, the soul of the artist must also be beautiful.

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